

Towards stress control in hard magnetic films

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Sputtering technologies are widely used to study functional materials. In the case of hard magnetic materials, the interest is 2-fold. On the one hand, films can be used to fabricate micro-magnets for applications in micro-devices. On the other hand, they can be used to study and optimize the extrinsic magnetic properties of the material itself. Compositionally graded films are now being used for the high throughput analysis of the effect of chemical composition and thermal treatments on the magnetic properties of hard magnetic. In all cases, film deposition at elevated temperatures and/or subsequent annealing can cause mechanical stress and deformation in the magnetic layer, as has been evidenced by the extrusion of a liquid secondary during annealing of NdFeB films [1]. Such mechanical stress may affect the lattice parameters and magnetic properties of the film, and may even lead to film fracture and/or delamination. Understanding and minimizing stress is important for both fundamental and applied studies.

Applying the theory of mechanical interaction of thin films in a composite system [2, 3], we propose methods to control stress formation in (Nd,La,Ce)FeB films. Using a multilayer composition with Ta as a buffer layer is an effective method to reduce stress in films [1]. However, the thickness of the layer is determined more by trial and error than by theory. For instance, in the Si-Ta-ReFeB system with thicknesses of Si-layer (0.5 mm) and ReFeB-layer (0.01 mm), our calculations showed a linear dependence between the required thickness of the tantalum layer (ranging from 0 to 0.004 mm) and the linear expansion coefficient of the target layer, achieving a near-zero stress level in the ReFeB magnetic layer. Another way to control stress is to use buffer materials with low yield strength to reduce stress in the adjacent layer. This method considers the plastic properties of the material and reduces stress near the system's external boundary, increasing the composite's resistance to delamination. Adjusting layer order, mechanical properties, thickness, and temperature during deposition can sometimes achieve desired stress levels. Choosing mechanical characteristics for stress control layers is complex and should be based on material databases, considering all available material properties and equipment limitations.

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References

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